

PROJECT CITIZEN MODIFICATION LEARNING MODEL BASED ON DIGITAL CITIZENSHIP FOR CHARACTER EDUCATION IN THE DIGITAL AGE AS AN EFFORT TO IMPROVE SOCIAL COMPETENCE

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ABSTRACT:

Citizenship Education as a strengthening of moral values needs to be developed by updating the development of the Project Citizen Learning Model. One knows this Project Citizen developmental update as Project Citizen Modification Based on Digital Citizenship. This is in line with the efforts made by the government synergistically in strengthening the nation's character. For this reason, this research develops civic education learning that can integrate character values and increase citizen knowledge and behavior that can reflect moral values in secondary schools. The research method in this research uses research and development. This study uses a procedural development model. There are five stages used in the research procedure, including: Analyze, Design, Develop, Implement and Evaluation. The name of the procedure is the ADDIE model. The sample in this study involved 163 high school students in Surakarta. The results showed that the learning design starting from the preliminary, main, and closing activities in the learning step included aspects of reflection on moral values, which were developed in the use of the Project Citizen Modification model in Civics learning. The internalization of moral values as a pillar of character development is in line with government policies that simultaneously and synergistically strengthen the nation's character. So that Civics learning can integrate the character values of citizens, which one can see in understanding and behavior that can reflect moral values. In addition, character education as a fundamental aspect is to help the realization of the national vision as required by the basic Indonesian principles regulated in the Indonesian constitution. This is very relevant to improve the social competence of citizens in the very diverse Digital Age. For this reason, the novelty of this research is to find intellectual attitudes as a bridge to the concept of social attitudes and spiritual attitudes that support the integration of social competence of citizens and digital information systems through Digital Citizenship.

Keywords: Project Citizen Modification, Character Education, Digital Citizenship, Social Competence

1. Introduction

The quality of character in the current reform era is very important for renewal and as a new paradigm. Moral degradation that occurs in society raises its own problems. For this reason, one needs concrete steps as curative actions as explained by Donie Koesuma (2007) that there are three dimensions: individual, social, and moral. There is a negative relationship between the individual and society. Education is at the forefront of making changes that are in line with the realization of curative actions, as explained above. When moral standards are ambiguous, it has a direct impact on moral cases that influence traditional customs. In moral character education, teaching principle through examples, advice, giving rewards and punishment were not effective in developing expected moral behavior as stated by Hartsthorne and May in Sarbaini, (2011). It is necessary to develop more effective and

innovative methods to develop traditional character education methods Budimansyah, D. (2010). Instilling character is not only the responsibility of a teacher, but the responsibility of the entire school community. The development of character education requires the support of all components in the school. All components carry the implementation out in the school. For this reason, the family and school environment become the next pillar besides those in society (Ministry of National Education, 2010). Furqon Hidayatullah, M. (2011) states other strategies that include exemplary, inculcating discipline, habituation to create a conducive atmosphere, and integration and internalization.

According to the Government Ordinance of Education and Culture number 69 of 2013, it divided the topic matters that can be taken and followed in Senior High School into two groups: Obligatory Subject Matters and Optional Subject Matters. Optional subject subjects include academics' selections for senior high school. This option colours the education unit's function, and there is a choice based on the learners' interests. This structure is according to the idea that learners are the subject of their learning, and they have the freedom to choose the subject that interests them. Obligatory subject topics are part of general education, which includes instruction in all civic qualities. Its goal is to provide learners with a better awareness of their country, national attitudes, and vital abilities to help them grow their own lives, societies, and countries.

Based on Rauner and Maclean (2008), they mentioned that a model is a replacement for a specific system that is genuinely directed for study and a specific experiment. Joyce, Weil, and Calhoun (2011) claim that the teaching and learning models are not dissimilar. "Teaching models are good learning models." As a result, the teacher in the learning process will assist learners in obtaining knowledge, ideas, skills, and ways of thinking, as well as determining facilities to communicate them, as well as how the instructor teaches the students in line with their learning style. According to the views expressed above, the term "learning model" has a broader definition in terms of strategy, technique, and procedure. In the subject of education, it frequently defined strategy as "planning that comprises a series of activities that attain a learning goal" Sanjaya, Vienna. (2010). Meanwhile, a method is a methodical approach to achieving a specific goal (Joyce, B & Weil M, 2009).

There is a need to implement character education that meets moral principles in civic education learning activities. To fulfil these principles, it depends on the ability of a teacher to build a model, which is based on three factors. First, there is no previous model; second, the current model exists, but it does not work very well; and third, as a variation of the existing model, it is likely to work well. As problem solving, this curriculum encourages students to actively take part in government and civil society. Ones expect students to develop their social and intellectual intelligence. Achieving these goals applies to the importance of increasing understanding of responsible democratic life. It is concrete form that contains in Project Citizen. The interpretation of the definition of Project Citizen is briefly as a problem-based learning method that aims to improve the knowledge, skills, and democratic image of citizens and encourage involvement in government and civil society. Historically, Project Citizen was first used and developed in California in 1992, by the Center

for Citizenship Education (CCE) and the State Council for the National Conference of Constitutionalists. Then, in 1995, the National Conference of the State Constitutional Body also developed Project Citizen.

Civic education learning has a vital part in the educational process because it may intelligently and effectively disclose all of an individual's potential for the benefit of society (Winataputra, Udin S: 2006). As a result, it is necessary to alter the notion of civic education learning so that it shifts from cognitive to multi-dimensional development of smart, democratic, and religious people. This reformation aims to transform learners into young citizens that are smart, creative, and participatory, have diverse perspectives, and are civically accountable in order to provide public policy recommendations to their communities. As we can see from the statement above, civic education currently more focuses on the cognitive part than the affective aspect. Civics education should all address Affective, cognitive, and psychomotor aspects. As a result, it needs reformation in terms of values and character: (1) Promotes the importance of core ethical ideals as the foundation of good character; (2) define "character" broadly to include one's thoughts, feelings, and actions; (3) Approaches character development in a thorough, intentional, proactive, and effective manner; (4) Foster a compassionate school environment; (5) Provides chances for students to take moral action; (6) Provides a meaningful and rigorous academic program that values all students, develops their character, and assists them in achieving their goals; (7) Encourages students to be self-motivated; (8) Involves the school personnel as a learning and moral community that shares responsibility for character education and tries to uphold some key ideals that govern kids' education; (9) Encourages shared moral leadership and long-term support for the character education endeavour, and (10) Makes families and community members partners in the effort to create character. Assesses the school's character, the school staff's ability to serve as character educators, and the extent to which students show good character (Lickona, T: 2003).

The reintroduction of nomenclature in civics education in the 2013 curriculum is a reaction to the worsening nationality situation in connection to national behavior and state life, both of which are at odds with the Five Principles (Pancasila). As a result, a humanistic learning process should be developed in which teaching learning process conditions are completely friendly, warm, and open in order for learners to be able to develop their full potential in order to be religious, smart, participative, democratic, and responsible civic virtues, so it is necessary to develop a humanistic learning process in which teaching learning process conditions are completely friendly, warm, and open. Norhayati, A. M., & Siew, P. H (2004) Moral Principles of Excellence Test and Application of Appreciation The purpose of the test is to provide a cognitive grasp of human conduct, to broaden life experiences, and to develop a sensitivity to moral sentiments as crucial instruments in coming to grips with human experience. In the meantime, the students can use the test to practice and improve their affective abilities. In the meantime, the students can use the test to practice and improve their affective abilities. Designing Interactive Multimedia Learning Environments for Moral Values Education from a Malaysian Perspective Incorporated into the moral education curriculum are sixteen good moral values. Compassion, self-reliance, respect, love, (5)

freedom, (6) courage, (7) physical and mental cleanliness, (8) cooperation, (9) diligence, (10) moderation, (11) thankfulness, (12) reason, (13) public spiritedness, (14) humility, (15) honesty, and (16) justice are among them. Each moral value is comprised of a number of sub-values.

To produce designs and systematically expand the form and results, implementing the model is through the complete design of the learning model to be developed. In the learning system, one of the development designs used in this research is the ADDIE model. The Civic Education learning in the 2013 curriculum, which places responsibility and character building in all subjects, adapts this model for the learning system with a wider scope. For this reason, there is the development of the main competencies, which include Spiritual Attitudes, Social Attitudes, Knowledge and Skills, based on the description of achievement indicators.

The civics education study in Curriculum 2013 placed responsibility for character education not only for the principles and civic education courses, but also for the core competency embracing spiritual attitude competency, social attitude competency, knowledge and skill vertically and horizontally (Trisiana, A: 2015).

There are four competencies that are very relevant and essential in facing the influence of the digital era, which is very complex and open. The four competencies are critical thinking and problem solving, and creativity. Then there are also competencies in the ability to communicate and cooperate. The four competencies will strengthen the implementation of character education, in which an educational unit conducts it, and all components of society drives it.

Under the description of the background above, Digital Citizenship is an alternative for the development of Modified Project Citizen, which is adapted to the development of information technology. This is in line with the concept of Digital Citizenship, where millions of people from various parts of the world have taken advantage of the presence of networking sites as a venue for digital interaction between one individual and another. Ones intend interaction in the virtual world as a place to share information as videos, e-books, pictures, and others.

2. Method

The researcher conducted this study at all senior high schools in Surakarta City. The sources of the data are primary and secondary sources. The primary data include informants, locales, and occurrences. The research sample in the limited test and the broad test on the Project Citizen learning model trial was 163 high school students. The Principal and stakeholders involved in developing Project Citizen's teaching approach in civic education are as informants who strengthen research data as primary data. In addition, secondary data in this study uses observations in implementing Civic Education learning in Surakarta City, which comes from the results of observations, and examines the learning tools used by Citizenship Education teachers who are members of the Civics Teacher Association at Senior High School.

This study focused on development research, not only in terms of producing or designing a teaching product, but also in terms of formulating a teaching approach that could be used as a teaching product in the classroom Borg, Walter R and Gall, Meredith D. (1987). The information gathered was made up of both primary and secondary sources. Information about behavior/informant, location, and events made up primary data. Information about behavior/informant, location, and events made up primary data. The informants were senior high school students and stakeholders involved in the construction of a model character project citizen in civics education in order to improve moral principles as the cornerstone of character education. The secondary data consists of linked papers from various civic education teaching and learning processes in Surakarta.

The procedural research development stage comprises five stages according to the ADDIE (Analysis-Design-Develop-Implement-Evaluate) model, including: (1) Analysis, namely conducting needs analysis (needs analysis), identifying problems (needs), and conducting task analysis (task analysis); (2) Design, formulating SMART learning objectives (Specific, Measurable, Applicable, Realistic, and Time-bound); (3) Development, making the blueprint alias design a reality. If the design requires software as multimedia learning; (4) Implementation is a real step to implement the learning system according to its role or function in order to implement the system; (5) Evaluation, the process to see whether the learning system being built is successful, under initial expectations or not (Steven. J.M: 2000).

3. Result and Discussion

3.1 Result

The researcher has developed a Project Citizen learning model that is in line with the achievement of citizenship education competencies. This is an alternative for teachers in developing and implementing student-focused learning models. In this development, the researcher designs the learning steps, which include introduction, core, and closing. The following explains each step:

3.1.1 Preliminary Activities: in this step, the teacher prepares students physically and psychologically, namely whether students are ready to follow the learning process. In addition, preliminary activities also focus on character values, equip students with learning motivation that is contextually related to the benefits and application of learning materials in everyday life, by providing examples of moral values and comparing local, national, and international examples; ask questions related to prior knowledge known as apperception. After that, the teacher conveys the basic competencies and indicators that to obtain as well as explaining the material and detailed explanation of activities under the basic competencies and indicators.

3.1.2 At the core stage of learning, it uses a scientific approach through the following order: (1) Explaining the facts under the presentation of basic competencies. (2) Using character values to identify the problem (Observing). (3) Based on character values, choosing

a problem to be discussed in class (Questioning). (4) Seeking information on issues (gathering information, and communication). (5) Creating a class portfolio based on personality traits (Networking). (6) Portfolio exhibition (Demonstrating). (7) Using character values to guide the learning experience (Conclusion). I adjust the discovery of problems in the core activities to the study of the material that has determined and adjusted to the learning indicators. The development paradigm in this activity rests on the affective domain, which begins with receiving, responding, appreciating, and ending with acting. The objectives of learning activities are according to the stages of competence, which motivate students to take part in them. Similarities and contrasts with learning activities in the psychomotor realm are to encourage students to produce creative and contextual work, both individually and in groups. I recommended students adopt learning strategies that result in problem solving based work. According to the observation guidelines in the psychomotor domain, I analyzed it based on studies on the topics and subtopics of learning materials. I associated it with the achievement of learning indicators in the material. To realize psychomotor learning, it is necessary to implement learning models based on moral values and learning that produce problem-based work.

3.1.3 Closing Activities: The final stage in this learning step is for teachers and students to reflect, namely by evaluating all stages of learning activities, as well as identifying the impact of learning both directly and indirectly. The impact of the learning relates to the change of the assessment that affects the change in attitude and behavior simultaneously. Then the teacher provides feedback and assignments that the follow-up is for the next meeting. (Trisiana, A: 2019)

3.2 Discussion

Problems that are increasingly diverse require the readiness of the world of education to expect and must move quickly to pick up the digital age with fast-paced and uncertain information. Students in this century must have the skills to determine their own learning goals (Self-Directed Learning), be able to construct knowledge (Knowledge Construction), can collaborate, communicate capable of utilizing ICT (using ICT), able to solve problems and innovation. The development of these skills is through integrating ICT into the learning process. Before we carry out innovative learning in the classroom, it is good we know in advance the character of the digital generation that is the subject of learning. Our students are now a generation of alpha genes and they have different characters from the previous Generation X and Y. Their character we need to know is:

- a. Independent: this generation lives and grows in digital freedom. Freedom to express themselves easily without distance and time and this has several implications on real life where they ask for freedom in their lives and lives;
- b. Fun: The digital generation tends to run their lives in a fun way;
- c. Expressive: Generations like this like to explore themselves. Almost all of them have their own preferences;

- d. Instant: Digital generation characters really need speed in what makes them impatient to achieve something;
- e. Explorative: They like to explore their experiences, they learn by doing technology support. They choose the media with the fastest feedback, video;
- f. Sharing: This generation is the largest producer of information in the digital world

Furthermore, Digital Citizenship relates to the ability to manage and monitor behavior in using technology, which includes security, ethics, norms, and culture; How should we use information technology safely, without causing harm and endangering the safety of ourselves and others; How should we communicate on social networks while maintaining ethics, referring to the norms that apply in the internal, national and universal environment; How should we transact information in cyberspace, especially in uploading/downloading content and transacting through online shops.

Based on the latest policy formulation, Citizenship Education in the 2013 Curriculum is a form of optimization to solve learning problems on a national scale that relies on the dominance of knowledge. Then switch to a new paradigm in democratic citizenship education. The policy basis is also relevant to the new paradigm of Citizenship Education related to the design of more innovative learning developments that are not obsolete with the times (Trisiana, A: 2020). At the same time, it can develop all the potentials of citizens to become citizens who have noble character, are intelligent, participatory, democratic, and responsible. This kind of citizenship character is the target and goal of humanistic education, which is relevant to the digital generation.

The center of Citizenship Education Learning is not only on the cognitive level, but can touch all levels integrative. Ones must carry out this fundamental change in line with the paradigm in the 2013 curriculum change, which carries the 5 M concept in learning. The preparation of learning tools can also adapt to the significant change. The creation of the component model is clearer, especially in the learning process, learning model, learning principles, support systems, instructional effects, and nurturing effects. Ones can study learning models for their effectiveness using phases such as orientation, hypothesis, definition, exploration, verification, and generalization.

Competency standards and basic competencies become the direction and basis for developing basic materials, activities, and indicators (Hui-Chuan Wei, Ai-Tzu Li, et all (2022). Competency standards and basic competencies are the directions and foundations for developing basic materials, learning activities, and indicators. In Citizenship Education, its focus is on the formation of citizens who understand and can carry out their rights and obligations to become intelligent, skilled, and characterized by Indonesian citizens mandated by Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution, Trisiana [17]. The above development direction is very relevant to the development of the 2013 curriculum. Students' responses to implementing Project Citizen become the basis for developing and measuring citizenship competencies that are formed as a learning impact.

The following is a table of student responses to implementing the Project Citizen learning model on Digital Era. The Digital Era is one challenge in developing citizenship competencies.

Table1. The Results of the Student Responses to Their Social Competence in the Digital Age on a limited test

No	Rated components	Average Score	Average Presentation Rating
1	Alertness (Be aware of what is going on around you and respond appropriately and correctly)	3.10	62 %
2	Analytical (Ability to describe in detail about the perception between concepts)	3.25	65%
3	Anticipatory (The reflection of an attitude that rests on courage, the determination to anticipate)	3.20	64%
4	Being careful and thorough in taking action before making the right decision.	3.24	64.8%
5	Able to be assertive and confident in expressing his abilities fairly, without harming others.	3.23	64.6%
6	Willingness (receiving orders responsibly in accordance with the plan).	3.45	69%
7	Virtue (Fulfils the principle of volunteerism and selflessness).	3.50	70%
8	Compassion (Having and showing affectionate feelings, loving and being gentle)	3.22	64.4%
9	Courage (Act persistently and righteously)	3.33	6%
10	Caring (Empathy and sympathy for others)	3.6	72%

According to Buchori [14], moral awareness leads to moral behavior through a procedure. Cognition (knowledge), attachment (feeling), volition (want), connotation (wish), motivation (incentive), and action are all part of this process (implementation). A variety of circumstances influence an individual's ability to put his or her values into practice. Changing an individual's behavior is difficult since it takes time and effort. An individual who is aware of moral ideals may implement them ineffectively, or not at all, in real or concrete action. The following results from the modification of the Project Citizen learning model based on Digital Citizenship in the Digital Era to Improve Social Competence:

1. Explaining Basic Competence Information; Training Sincerity, patience, thoroughness, and the capacity to discriminate between general and specialized information.
2. Identifying Problems Based on Character Values; Develop creativity, curiosity, and the ability to pose questions in order to build critical minds capable of living smart and long lives while learning.
3. Choosing problems to be discussed in class based on character values by creating a meticulous attitude, which is honest, polite, and respectful of others' opinions; adopting the ability to collect information through various modes of learning; and developing a lifelong learning habit.
4. Gathering information relevant to the chosen problems by cultivating an honest attitude, thoroughness, discipline, obedience to the rules, workaholic, process implementation capability, and the ability to think inductively and deductively in drawing conclusions.
5. Providing Poster Media; Creativity and Honesty, as well as respect for other people's work and other countries.
6. Reflection of learning experiences directly or indirectly, as an alternative formulation of public policy in handling problems involving experts.

John Dewey in developing the Project Citizen Model which was later reduced by researchers to Project Citizen Modification, this is appropriate with character education. Various government policy programs align the development of character-based Citizenship Education, and the development increases the participation of students to become skilled, critical, and responsible citizens [16]. Spiritual and social attitudes as attitudes in this study produce novelty as a continuation of implementing character education. This refers to as the instructional impact and the accompaniment impact in learning from main competencies in the 2013 curriculum, in the realm of attitudes. The following is a table regarding the results of the responses to implementing Project Citizen in Improving Citizenship Competence.

Table2. The implementation of Project Citizen in Improving Social Competence for Character Education

No	Rated components	Average Score	Average Presentation Rating
INTELLECTUAL ATTITUDE			
1	Alertness (be more careful in responding)	3.15	63%
2	Analytical (behave and behave logically in explaining a concept)	3.24	64.8%
3	Anticipatory (the emergence of courage, to take anticipatory action)	3.41	68.2%
4	Prudence, careful in determining the right decision before taking action.	3.35	67%
SPIRITUAL ATTITUDE			
5	The existence of assertiveness in expressing emotions and skills without harming others.	3.65	73%
6	Willingness (always ready to serve and consider personal plans and priorities secondary).	3.5	70%
7	Virtue providing for the basic needs of others without a motive for personal praise/reward.	3.53	70.6%
SOCIAL ATTITUDE			
8	Compassion (having and showing affectionate feelings, loving and being gentle)	3.41	68.2%
9	Courage (doing what is considered right, right, and just)	3.53	70.6%
10	Caring (ready to help people who need help, never be rude and hurt others, care about the environment)	3.5	70%

Social competence includes the ability to adapt to the demands of work and the environment. The manifestation of social competence is as a person's social participation in daily life in the community where he is, both formally and informally.

Table3. Pretest and Posttest Frequency Distribution

No	Score Interval	Pre-test		Post-test	
		Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
1	9,1 – 10	7	4.29	11	6.75
2	8,1 – 9	0	0.00	8	4.91
3	7,1 – 8	0	0.00	34	20.86
4	6,1 – 7	12	7.36	78	47.85
5	5,1 – 6	71	43.56	21	12.88
6	4,1 – 5	8	4.91	11	6.75
7	3,1 – 4	31	19.02	0	0.00
8	2,1 – 3	1	0.61	0	0.00
9	1,1 – 2	33	20.25	0	0.00
10	0 – 1	0	0	0	0.00

The type of social competence in the digital era, which citizens must possess, is as follows [17]:

- a. Skillful in communicating with the surrounding community
- b. Be sympathetic
- c. Can work together with the social environment.
- d. Good at getting along with the social environment.
- e. Understand the world around it (the Environment).
- f. Wise use of social media

Creating a young generation who handles the safety and glory of the homeland is the next goal. This sense is as the active participation of the younger generation in development. They will filter out influences from outside, take the positive side and reject things that are not under the noble values and morals of the nation. Finally, the expectation of civic education is to foster loyalty to the homeland and be sincerely willing to contribute every potential for the advancement of the homeland, even though it gets the lure of popularity or wealth from other parties.

In the digital era, of course, it needs to instill the values of nationalism through digital literacy, so that people can use Pancasila as a barrier to understanding that undermines state sovereignty. For that we need a digital culture, namely: (a) basic knowledge of Pancasila and Bhinneka Tunggal Ika as the basis for culture, national and Indonesian language life; (b) basic knowledge of distinguishing any information that is not in line with Pancasila values on searching engines; (c) basic knowledge of knowing the importance of multiculturalism and diversity, as well as understanding how to preserve regional languages, arts, and culture in the digital space; (d) basic knowledge that encourages behavior to love domestic products, as well as understanding the right to access freedom of expression and intellectual property rights in the digital world.

4. Conclusion

Implementing the Modification of Project Citizen model in civic education at the high school level in improving the competence of citizens in the Digital Age has resulted in strengthening attitudes. The intellectual attitude is the improvement of the affective domain that affects social attitudes, social skills, and spiritual attitudes. Civic education competence, which is described as integrated character education, which includes civic knowledge, civic skills, and civic disposition, is very important to adapt in all times, which prioritizes a mature intellectual attitude.

Being nurtured and cultivated throughout time is also a must for children's creativity and activity. As a pedagogical effort, character education aims to help each individual completely appreciate his or her uniqueness. Social competence in Indonesian society today is not merely

a consumer in the era of world technological progress. Indonesian society must also be a part of creators in the world of technology as well.

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